

IDENTIFICATION OF IDEAL LIGHT PRUNING TIME FOR SMALL HOLDING TEA PLANTATIONS IN THE CHATTOGRAM HILL TRACTS

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Abstract

One of the most crucial operations in tea cultivation is pruning, in which the branches of the tea bushes are slash down at a predetermined height to reinvigorate the bush and bring it within the pluckers range. Pruning also helps to maximize the yield and quality. Among the pruning operations practiced, Light Pruning (LP) is one of the drastic and vital operations that has significant impact on tea production and quality. Recovery potential of a tea plant after pruning depends on many factors among which time of pruning plays an important role because of the surrounding environmental conditions. In this context, the current study was conducted to identify the best time of LP in the Chattoqram Hill Tracts of Bangladesh. Starting from 1st November, seven different dates were tested maintaining about 20 days interval. Results showed that significantly highest number of plucking points/bush/round (42.33) and yield (2400 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained when LP was done on 10th December, followed by 30th December and 20th November. Significantly the lowest number of plucking points/bush/round (27.33) and yield (1267 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained when LP was done on 1st March and it was followed by 10th February. Considering the mortality percentage after pruning, it was observed that no mortality was observed when pruning was done on 1st November, 20th November, 10th December and 30th December. On the contrary, highest mortality (4.44%) was observed when pruning was done on 10th February followed by 1st March and 20th January. From the findings, 10th December was identified as the ideal time of LP for the tea plantations in the Chattoqram hill tracts of Bangladesh for higher productivity.

Keywords: Tea, Pruning time, Light Pruning, Hill tracts

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Introduction

One of the most popular beverages consumed worldwide is tea. *Camellia sinensis*, the tea plant, is grown in roughly 30 different nations (Adnan et al., 2013). Although it originated in South Eastern China, it is now grown in several tropical and subtropical areas across the world and contains more than 82 genetically distinct species (Krafczyk & Glomb, 2008; Sultana et al., 2008; Akhlas et al., 2003). A tea plant naturally develops into a tiny tree, but successive pruning and other silvicultural techniques, such as tipping, plucking, and harvesting the best vegetative product, transform it into a bush (Kumar et al., 2015). Next to plucking, pruning is one of the most crucial operations that affect productivity and quality of tea (TTRA, 2008). To rejuvenate and bring tea bushes within reach of the pluckers, pruning is the clipping of tea bush branches at a certain height and at a predetermined interval. Pruning is necessary to control apical dominance, maintain bushes in the vegetative stage, and direct energy toward the formation of leaves. Additionally, it promotes branching, which results in more tender leaves (Ravichandran, 2004).

Generally, the tea planters of North East India and Bangladesh consider December to January as optimal time to prune tea bushes. During this period tea plant has optimum level of starch reserve in tea roots (Sarma, 2023). The regeneration of the tea bush as well as the carbohydrate balance of the root and shoot system is greatly impacted by deep pruning (Bore et al., 2003). Qamar et al. (2011) reported the highest shoot growth (71.33 cm) and fresh leaf output from tea plantations that were pruned in December. Maximum plucking points in tea plants pruned in early November and receiving 240 kg N ha⁻¹ were also recorded by Hamid et al. (2000). According to Hajra (2001), the optimal period for tea pruning in North East India is between December and January when the starch reserve in the roots is completely grown.

In the 1840s, tea farming in Bangladesh began in the area of the Chittagong Club. The first tea garden in Bangladesh was established in Sylhet in 1854 and it began producing tea commercially in 1857 (BTB, 2023). Since 2002, the tea cultivation was also introduced in the northern parts of the country namely Panchagarh, Lalmonirhat, Thakurgaon, Nilphamari, Dinajpur and the southern district Bandarban in the Chattogram Hill Tracts. To extend small holding tea cultivation and to provide suitable technologies to the growers of Chattogram Hill Tracts (Bandarban sadar, Rowangchari and Ruma upazila), Ministry of Commerce of Bangladesh has launched a project titled as 'Extension of Small Holding Tea Cultivation in Chattogram Hill Tracts in the year 2016 (BTB, 2023). Pruning operations mostly depends on time, topography and climate. As the topography and climate of Chattogram Hill Tracts is completely different than the other tea growing regions of the country, it is necessary to identify the ideal pruning time for this region. Among the pruning operations practiced, Light Pruning (LP) is the most vital one and has a substantial impact on yield and quality. Therefore, the current research was carried out to observe the effect of different light pruning time on crop yield and identify the best time for higher productivity in the Chattogram Hill Tracts of Bangladesh.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was carried out in a 12-years old mature tea (BT2) section of small holding tea planter Mr. Osman Goni in Bandarban sadar, Bandarban Hill Tracts during the period of November 2020 to December 2021. Three replications of the experiment were done using a randomized complete block design (RCBD). There were seven treatments of the experiment. Starting from 1st November 2020, light pruning completed at different dates maintaining about 20 days interval were the treatments of the experiment. The treatments were denoted as T1 (LP on 1st November), T2 (LP on 20th November), T3 (LP on 10th December), T4 (LP on 30th December), T5 (LP on 20th January), T6 (LP on 10th February) and T7 (LP on 1st March), respectively. Pruning of tea bushes and fertilizer applications were done according to the BTRI recommendation (BTRI, 1994; BTRI, 1986). There was no irrigation facility in the experimental site and hence the experiment was fully depended on rain water. Five (5) layers of tipping allowance were given to each bush. Plucking was carried out mostly at weekly interval and the related data were collected. Data were collected on (a) Number of shoots plucked per bush (plucking points) per round, (b) Weight of the shoots per bush per round to calculate the green leaf yield (kg ha⁻¹) and (c) Mortality (%) of the tea bushes after pruning. Data were analyzed statistically with the help of MSTATC software.

Results and Discussion

Effect of light pruning time on number of plucking points

It was observed that the number of plucking points is significantly impacted by pruning time (Table 1). The treatment T3 (LP on 10th December) produced significantly highest number of plucking points/bush/round (42.33), which was followed by T4 (LP on 30th December), T2 (LP on 20th November), T1 (LP on 1st November), T5 (LP at 20th January) and T6 (LP on 10th February). Significantly the lowest number of plucking points/bush/round (27.33) was obtained in T7 (LP on 1st March). The plucking points obtained in T3 and T4 are statistically comparable to each other. Similarly, the plucking points obtained in T4, T2, T1 and T5 are comparable to each other. The lowest plucking points obtained in T7 are also comparable with T6.

Table 1. Effect of light pruning at different times on the number of plucking points.

Treatments	Plucking points (per bush per round)
T1 (LP on 1st November)	34.66bc
T2 (LP on 20th November)	37.66b
T3 (LP on 10th December)	42.33a
T4 (LP on 30th December)	41.33ab
T5 (LP on 20th January)	34.33bc
T6 (LP on 10th February)	30.66cd
T7 (LP on 1st March)	27.33d
LSD at 5% level of significance	8.33
CV (%)	13.16

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

From the results, a gradual decline in the number of plucking points/bush/round was observed in the treatments after 10th December (T3). This result is in accordance with the result of [Ahmad et al. \(2014\)](#) who reported that most plucking points were produced by tea bushes when pruned on December 10th.

Effect of light pruning time on green leaf yield

Satisfactory recovery of the tea bushes after pruning and the productivity of the bushes depends on many factors including the type and level of intensity of pruning, condition, activity, and reserves of the root system, timing of pruning, tea bush health which reflects pruning techniques used in the past, nutrition of the bush, soil quality, rainfall patterns, and temperature ([TRIT, 2004](#)). In this study, different time of LP was tested to identify the best time specific to the Chattogram Hill Tracts of Bangladesh as the topography and climate of this region is completely different than the other tea growing regions of the country. From the result (Table 2), it was observed that significantly highest green leaf yield of 2400 kg ha⁻¹ was obtained in the treatment T3 (LP on 10th December), which was followed by T4 (LP on 30th December), T2 (LP on 20th November), T5 (LP on 20th January), T1 (LP on 1st November) and T6 (LP on 10th February). Significantly the lowest yield of 1267 kg/ha was obtained in T7 (LP on 1st March). Statistically, the highest yield from T3 is comparable with the yields from T4, T2 and T5. Again, the yields from T4, T2, T5 and T1 are comparable with each other. The lowest yield from T7 is also comparable with the yield from T1.

Table 2. Effect of light pruning at different times on the yield of tea.

Treatments	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)
T1 (LP on 1 st November)	1767bcd
T2 (LP on 20 th November)	2033abc
T3 (LP on 10 th December)	2400a
T4 (LP on 30 th December)	2350ab
T5 (LP on 20 th January)	1950abc
T6 (LP on 10 th February)	1500cd
T7 (LP on 1 st March)	1267d
LSD at 5% level of significance	621.39
CV (%)	14.29

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

According to [Satyanarayana et al. \(1994\)](#), effective pruning promotes improved branching, which results in more tender leaves. If timing of pruning is appropriate, maximum number of shoots can be generated that is helpful to maximize production. In this study, plucking point was highest in treatment T3 (Table 1) and the yield was also highest in the same treatment (Table 2). It is known that for proper recovery, pruning should be done in such a time when the bushes are in dormant stage and have enough starch reserve to withstand the shock and further regrowth. It was observed that the bushes of the experimental site were at complete dormant stage in early December. Most probably the starch reserve was highest at this time and hence the highest yield was obtained in the treatment T3 (LP on 10th December). At the NTRI tea garden, [Hamid et al. \(2002\)](#) found that pruning during the dormant season resulted in the largest production of fresh tea leaves per bush.

Effect of light pruning time on mortality (%) of the tea bushes

It was shown that the timing of pruning had a significant impact on the mortality (%) of tea bushes (Table 3). Significantly the highest mortality (%) of 4.44 was recorded in the treatment T6 (LP on 10th February), which is statistically similar with the mortality from the treatments T5 (LP on 20th January) and T7 (LP on 1st March). No mortality was found in the treatments T1 (LP on 1st November), T2 (LP on 20th November), T3 (LP on 10th December) and T4 (LP on 30th December).

The tea plant's starch reserves, according to Chakrabarty & Barpujari (1992), are a key factor in determining when to prune since new growth depends on the reserves, and pruning in any form without an appropriate store of carbohydrates might be devastating. With pruning operation, a large volume of the foliage and young shoots is removed off resulting in cessation of carbohydrate synthesizing activities of the plants. Thus, the initial growth of new developing shoots for formation of bush frame and recover from pruning is supported by the carbohydrate reserve in the roots (Selvendran & Selvendran, 1972). After pruning, it was seen that the amount of root reserves significantly decreased (Wijeratne et al., 2002). Availability of adequate soil moisture is also important for translocation of starch from root-serve to the growing points. Severe moisture stress may reduce root carbohydrate concentrations but may faster its consumption in the droughty areas (Marimuthu et al., 1996; Barman et al., 1998).

Table 3. Effect of light pruning at different times on mortality (%) of tea bushes.

Treatments	Mortality (%)
T1 (LP on 1 st November)	0
T2 (LP on 20 th November)	0
T3 (LP on 10 th December)	0
T4 (LP on 30 th December)	0
T5 (LP on 20 th January)	2.22a
T6 (LP on 10 th February)	4.44a
T7 (LP on 1 st March)	2.22a
LSD at 5% level of significance	6.34
CV (%)	11.22

Within column values followed by different letter (s) are significantly different by DMRT ($p \leq 0.05$)

In the Chattogram hill tracts, rain flush is generally available till late November and starts again from April-May. Therefore, acute water scarcity is observed from the beginning of the year to till April-May. In the present study, the plants light pruned after December most probably suffered due to shortage of food reserve due to drought condition, and hence the mortality is high in the treatments T5 (LP on 20th January), T6 (LP on 10th February) and T7 (LP on 1st March). On the other hand, no mortality was observed in the treatments where light pruning was completed before or within December, probably due to the better starch reserve at the time of pruning and the bushes could alleviate the drought condition easily as demand of water was less due to defoliation by pruning.

Conclusion

Light pruning at different times had significant effect on the yield of tea. Considering the number of plucking points/bush and yield, higher performances were observed when light pruning was completed within December; and more specifically, the highest performances was on 10th December. Higher bush mortality (%) was observed when light pruning was carried out after December. Therefore, it can be concluded that mid-December (within 10th December) is the ideal time for Light Pruning for maximum crop production and lower bush mortality (%) in the Chattogram hill tracts of Bangladesh.

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